

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring
data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D2.9 Prioritised inventory of unavailable data sources

27/02/2025

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D2.9 – Prioritised inventory of unavailable data sources

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
Bio Eco Portal	UNESCO's GOOS Biology and Ecosystems Metadata Portal
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EDIOS	European Directory of Ocean Observing Systems
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EurOBIS	European node of OBIS
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
IMIS	Integrated Marine Information System
MARCO-BOLO	Marine Coastal Biodiversity Long-term Observations
MBA	Marine Biological Association
MEDIN	Marine Environmental Data and Information Network
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
URI	Unique Resource Identifier
URL	Unique Resource Locator
VLIZ	Flanders Marine Institute
WFD	Water Framework Directive

WKT	Well-Known Text
WP	Work Package

Keywords

Digital Twin Ocean, data accessibility, marine biodiversity data, data inventory

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

DTO-BioFlow aims to target current challenges in the accessibility, collection and harmonization of data. This deliverable addresses the accessibility element, identifying and prioritizing currently unavailable datasets and potential data sources for ingestion to primary and secondary integrators that will connect to the Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) data repositories. The outcomes of this deliverable will inform the second data grants call for the subsequent evaluation of the data call. An initial list of 436 data sources were collated from the European Directory of Ocean Observing Systems (EDIOS) and the UNESCO's GOOS Bio Eco Portal, and additional sources identified by other DTO-Bioflow work packages as inaccessible and required for their tasks. The initial assessment of inaccessibility for these datasets came across limitations such as slight differences in spelling or wording of the titles of datasets. In some cases, this made it unclear whether these are actually accessible via integrators such as EurOBIS, or if they are subsets or different versions of the available datasets. This led to a second accessibility assessment which incorporated information from anywhere in the metadata rather than just titles to determine if datasets were accessible. The resulting list of 303 inaccessible datasets, i.e. data not available for users to find and access or download, has been prioritized by using a scoring system based on a set of criteria including spatial coverage, taxonomic coverage, variables measured, the type of data, whether they are a time series and whether they are required internally by DTO work packages to conduct their work within the DTO-BioFlow project. This list can be downloaded from the [DTO-Bioflow website](#). The prioritisation process identified 40 high-priority datasets which should be the initial targets for data mobilisation efforts, including 15 datasets specifically identified and required by WP3 of DTO-BioFlow. In addition to the prioritisation, the inventory lists necessary metadata to ease the mobilisation of datasets into the DTO to 'unlock' these datasets and make them available.

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1. Collation and prioritisation of data

1.1 Collation of inaccessible datasets

A summary of the methodology followed to create the inventory can be seen in Figure 1. A total of 436 datasets were collated as an initial working inventory from three main sources: the European Directory of Ocean Observing Systems (EDIOS), the Global Ocean Observing System's (GOOS) Bio Eco Portal, and specific inaccessible datasets (where data cannot be found or accessed by a user) identified by DTO-Bioflow's WP3, where raw DNA data are available but not the processed data including species occurrences. EDIOS and the GOOS Bio Eco Portal were selected as they provide long term observations and therefore list potential high value datasets, in addition to a link to wider global interoperability. The dataset titles originating from EDIOS were obtained using the parameters in the query found [here](#), including all European datasets. The query filters European datasets by those that include the following parameter groups: bacteria and viruses, biota abundancy, biomass and diversity, biota composition, birds, mammals and reptiles, fish, fisheries, habitat, microzooplankton, other biological measurements, phytoplankton and microphytobenthos, rate measurements (including production, excretion and grazing), rock and sediment biota and zooplankton. Those from the GOOS Bio Eco Portal were titles of European metadata records in GOOS which did not have a download URL which resolved to a location where data can be accessed. A template was created containing metadata fields relevant for the prioritisation process to target the inaccessible datasets. The template and the metadata fields selected were based on the metadata template used in the MARCO-BOLO project to collate metadata from datasets produced within said project, the information provided from the EDIOS list, and the previous DTO-BioFlow data call template collated by VLIZ. Table 1 shows the descriptions of the fields within the metadata template.

Figure 1 – Overview of the method followed to create the inventory.

The inventory was subjected to two accessibility assessments. The first involved a search of each title from EDIOS online (search engine such as Google) and a search on the [MEDIN Discovery Metadata Portal](#), which includes metadata for a number of UK-based records (for those records from EDIOS which were UK-based), to assess whether the data could be found, accessed online and downloaded by a user. A list of 190 inaccessible datasets identified from the [GOOS Bio Eco Portal](#) was provided by UNESCO in the agreed template format. This list was not assessed at this stage as the criteria for inclusion in the initial list was to only have titles for records which did not have a data access and download location. However, this posed an issue as many of these datasets were later found to be accessible online under slightly different titles or through links which were not listed in the metadata records found on the GOOS Bio Eco Portal. A comparison of all titles against the list of datasets found on EurOBIS was carried out, with one being found here, and a further seven were found to be accessible on either EMODnet Biology or the Helcom Biodiversity database ([Data – HELCOM](#)) following internal review by DTO-Bioflow WP2 participants. These were removed from the first submission of the inventory. The remaining datasets were identified by WP3 as inaccessible and were added to the inventory and marked as internal requests in the “DTOInternal” column, with the barriers to access added to the “Barriers” column. Table 2 shows the initial and final numbers of datasets following this assessment.

A second accessibility assessment was carried out, where the initial inventory of 422 inaccessible datasets were re-assessed by searching for each title online but also incorporating any relevant information from the metadata available e.g. in the abstracts in order to assist with finding datasets which were accessible under different titles, within larger datasets, or where the data were available as multiple subsets within the project. The dataset availability on EMODnet was also assessed using the IMIS (Integrate Marine Information System) dataset search: IMIS | Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee. The results of this second assessment are summarised in Table 3, with the 303 still classed as inaccessible, and 85 being accessible, and a further 12 being removed due to duplication in EDIOS and the GOOS Bio Eco Portal. Nonetheless, this list should be taken with caution as the datasets could be openly available as subsets of the data or be contained within a larger dataset. 19 datasets, listed in Annex II, were classed as inaccessible as they either require a login or credentials to access the data, or they can only be obtained by requesting the data; whilst it is likely these are accessible, we were not able to confirm this during the assessment so they were removed from the final list. Further detail on the barrier to accessibility of the remaining datasets in the inventory is recorded in the “Barrier” column.

Table 1 – Field descriptions for the template of metadata collected from the inaccessible datasets.

Field	Description
DatasetIdentifier	Identifier for the dataset, providing link to the metadata.
Organisation	Organisation to which the dataset contact belongs. Free text.
DatasetTitle	A title for the dataset. Free text.
ProjectTitle	Title for the project/programme/series if there is one. Free text.
DatasetDescription	A brief description of the dataset. Free text.
InProgress	Yes/No, if the dataset is still in progress.
DataStartDate	The start date of the data in the dataset. Format: YYYY-MM-DDThh.mm (time is optional).
DataEndDate	The end date of the data in the dataset. Format: YYYY-MM-DDThh.mm (time is optional).
MetadataUpdateDate	If known, date when the metadata for the dataset was last updated.
SpatialCoverageMarineRegion	The spatial coverage entered as Marine Regions URLs where possible, or free text. If using Marine Regions (https://www.marineregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=search), use the MRGID URLs (e.g. https://marineregions.org/mrgid/1234) here. Separate values with a " " character.
WKT	If known, the WKT for the polygon of the dataset survey area.

Variables/TaxonomicCoverage	Variables and taxa covered by the dataset e.g. link from WoRMS or NCBI or variables from controlled vocabularies e.g. https://geonode.goosoocean.org//api/keywords/ , and be entered as a URI (https://...) or free text. Where the species list is long, either list all species, list the genus, or use a term for the class of organism using a controlled vocabulary such as WoRMS or NCBI, including a full URL. Separate values with a " " character.
DataType	Broad type of data e.g. genomic, eDNA, citizen science. Free text.
Barrier	If known, reason why the dataset is inaccessible. Free text.
Time series	If known, whether the dataset is part of a time series. If the term "time series" is present in any part of the metadata for the dataset, it is classed as a time series. Binary, yes or no.

Table 2 – Number of initial and final datasets following assessment of inaccessibility.

Source	Initial number of datasets	Number of datasets after first assessment
EDIOS	231	225
GOOS Bio Eco Portal	190	181
DTO-BioFlow work packages	15	15

Table 3 – Outcome of the second accessibility assessment.

Outcome	Number of datasets
Inaccessible	303
Inaccessible due to login being required or data only available by request – listed in Annex II	19
Accessible	49
Accessible but title doesn't match exactly	33
Accessible as multiple subsets from the same project	6

1.2 Prioritisation

A total of 303 inaccessible datasets were prioritised based on these criteria including: whether they were part of a known time series, their age (years from start date), the spatial coverage, taxonomic coverage, variables measured, the type of data and whether they were requested internally by a DTO-BioFlow Work Package to be able to complete their activities. To prioritise the datasets, they receive a score for each prioritisation criterium. Priority score values range from 1 to 3, with 1 being the lower priority and 3 being a high priority score). Table 4 shows the prioritisation criteria and how each of the score values is defined for these criteria. Whilst specific, named inaccessible datasets identified by WP3 and added to the inventory and scored as 9 under DTOInternal, more general requirements from WP4 for data types, spatial and taxonomic coverage were incorporated into the prioritisation scoring for those fields. The initial draft for the prioritisation included fields such as license, and any known data gaps i.e. whether the data was missing data

from certain regions or time periods, but these were removed from the prioritisation criteria due to a lack of clear information about these for the selected list of datasets.

A total sum of scores across fields was calculated for each dataset. This final score was used to rank datasets and the top 10%, 25% and 50% cut offs were used to identify a final prioritisation (10% = high priority, <50% = low priority). In addition to this, a max score was included which shows the single highest score across fields. Datasets identified as inaccessible by WP3 were marked as DTOInternal, with a score of 9 to create a weighting that identified these internally required datasets as the highest priority. Scores of 3 were the highest score allocated other than in the DTOInternal field, and scores of 0 were assigned where insufficient metadata was available to make an assessment, or where the value was not specified as being of high importance to mobilise the data within the DTO-BioFlow project, due to current data coverage or WP needs.

*Table 4 – Scoring matrix used for scoring datasets against each field with scores 1-3 based on priority cases (e.g. 1 is lower priority while 3 is a high priority score). *Specific spatial coverages for the datasets are reflected in the WKT column as the well-known text for the polygons of those areas. **Note a multiplier has been applied to grant internal dataset requests with a score of 9 to ensure they are identified as high priority (top 10%), 9 was the minimum score to ensure internal datasets be in the top 10%.*

Field	0/no score	1	2	3	9
TimeSeries	unknown	no		Yes	Not applicable
DataAge	unknown	1-5 years Data and metadata likely to be within the lifespan of a project and being actively created/updated	6-10 yrs Data and metadata likely to be beyond the lifespan of a project, so more likely to be “sleeping” data but still be managed	>10 years old Data and metadata least likely to be actively managed, more likely to be “sleeping” data with highest risk of being lost due to change of roles/retirement of data managers	Not applicable
SpatialCoverage	Any spatial coverage not listed as priority 1, 2 or 3		Areas or countries which border or are within the priority 3 requested regions*: Norway, Netherlands, Belgium, Faeroe islands, Ireland, United Kingdom, France, Greenland, Iceland, Italy, Spain, Morocco, Malta, Greece, Turkey, Albania, Slovenia, Croatia, Latvia, Estonia, Finland, Denmark, Germany, Poland, Sweden, Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Georgia, Russian Federation	Areas from which data has been specifically requested by other DTO-BioFlow WPs: offshore, North Sea, North Atlantic, Mediterranean, Baltic Sea, Portugal, Black Sea	Not applicable

Taxonomic Coverage	Any taxa not listed as priority 1, 2 or 3			Datasets including taxa specifically requested by DTO work packages or identified as having low coverage: plankton, starfish, marine mammals, seabass, harbour porpoise, seaweeds, <i>Laminaria ochroleuca</i> , <i>Saccorhiza polyschides</i> , seagrass, <i>Sarpa salpa</i> , reptiles, seabirds	Not applicable
Variables Measured	Any not listed as priority 1, 2 or 3			Specific requests from other WPs: mariculture, MPA, carbon sequestration, chlorophyllA, human activities, underwater sound, turbidity, carbon flux, plankton biomass, traits, MSFD raw data, WFD raw data, genetic monitoring	Not applicable
Data Type	Any not listed as priority 1, 2 or 3		Data types either inferred from the variables measured requests from other WPs, or identified as being of relevance to DTO-BioFlow: genomics, citizen science, eDNA, acoustic		Not applicable
DTO Internal	unknown	No			Yes **

The prioritisation process identified 40 high priority datasets, listed in Annex I, which are the initial targets for future mobilisation efforts and targeted acquisition for activities beyond the lifespan of DTO-BioFlow. These will inform the second data grants call being carried out by WP2 for the resulting evaluation of applications and to advertise the call to the priority datasets.

2. Conclusions

A list of 303 inaccessible datasets has been produced as an inventory in the format of a spreadsheet, available on the [DTO-Bioflow website](#). The prioritisation process identified 40 high-priority datasets which should be the initial targets for data mobilisation efforts, including 15 DNA datasets specifically identified and where processed species occurrence data are required by WP3 of DTO-BioFlow. The assessment of inaccessibility for these datasets came across limitations such as slight differences in spelling or wording of the titles of datasets making it in some cases unclear whether these are accessible via integrators such as EuroBIS, or if they are subsets or different versions of the available datasets. A second in-depth inaccessibility assessment was carried out to address these limitations, but in some cases where metadata was insufficient to match the listed dataset to accessible datasets or projects, the corresponding datasets have been kept in the final inventory as inaccessible, and datasets where a login or data request process is required to access the data have been removed from the list and included in Annex II as they are likely to be available but this was not possible to be confirmed during the assessment.

3. Annex I

Datasets scoring the top 10% highest scores according to the prioritisation criteria.

Title	Dataset Identifier	Total score
The IOW Baltic Sea Time Series	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/468	16
Development of an autonomous biosampler to capture in situ aquatic microbiomes	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB27645	12
Detection of a Diverse Marine Fish Fauna using Environmental DNA from Seawater Samples	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB3120	12
Shotgun metagenome sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB40760	12
Shotgun metagenome sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB40764	12
eDNA samples from Danish boulder reefs	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB48452	12
COI metabarcoding study of pelagic ARMS communities deployed in Mendexa, Basque Country	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB63262	12
This study includes sequences from the ARMS deployed in Antarctica and included in the analyses of the publication Cecchetto et al. (2024) - Seasonality of primary production explains the richness of pioneering benthic communities.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB67891	12
Arabian Peninsula ARMS	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA1063439	12
Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structure Red Sea Latitudinal Raw Reads	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA479721	12
Cryptobiome COI raw reads	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA485689	12
DEVOTES ARMS	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA557002	12
Cabled observatories as multidisciplinary platforms for marine fish community monitoring	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA660323	12
Seq' and ARMS shall find: DNA (meta)barcoding of Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures across the tree of life uncovers hidden cryptobiome of tropical urban coral reefs	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA801066	12
18S rRNA sequences Palmyra Atoll National Wildlife Refuge	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA804389	12
Basque monitoring network for the ecological status assessment	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/142	12
Swedish National Monitoring	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/593	12

DK-D03-08 Mobile species - distribution, abundance and/or biomass - pelagic fish - Survey NHAS	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/784	12
FISH-PRO III - Baltic Sea Coastal Fish Monitoring Program (Russia)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/896	10
Deep Sea Benthic Biodiversity Project	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/978	12
Historic Benthic Monitoring	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10059	10
Dove Marine Station Long Term Monitoring	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10084	10
Seabird Monitoring Programme	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10104	10
Transitional and Coastal Water Framework Directive (WFD) Water Column Monitoring	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10127	10
Natural Resources Wales (NRW) Skomer Marine Conservation Zone Monitoring	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10256	10
Jellyfish Survey	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10265	10
Delfini del Ponente - Dolphin Research Project	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/962	11
DK-D03-09 Mobile species - distribution, abundance and/or biomass - pelagic fish - Survey IESNS	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/785	11
ANSBE-P11-Fisheries-dependent observer-at-sea programme - Common Fisheries Policy	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/758	10
Seabed habitats - community characteristics, Water column variables	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/766	10
Bulgarian National Monitoring - Black Sea macrosites	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/768	10
DK-D06-09 Benthic species - abundance and/or biomass	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/789	10
Coastal Observing System for Northern and Arctic Seas (COSYNA)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/803	10
Editing details for LTER North Sea Benthos Observatory	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/808	10
Icelandic Phytoplankton monitoring programme	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/812	10
Engure marine site	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/823	10
FISH-PRO III - Baltic Sea Coastal Fish Monitoring Program (Germany)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/922	10
European Temperature and Biodiversity Observation Network	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/931	10
HELCOM Marine breeding birds abundance and distribution	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/980	10
HELCOM Phytoplankton Pigments	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/983	10

4. Annex II

Datasets removed from the inventory as they are likely to be available, but access requires credentials or must be via data request.

Title	Identifier
Plankton biodiversity monitoring by environmental DNA: a multiple marker study	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJDB12325
Littoral Environment Observation Service	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/11351
Mediterranean Ocean Observing System for the Environment (ILICO - MOOSE)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/747
Marine Mammals Exploring the Oceans Pole to Pole - Norway	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/884
Wetland Bird Survey (WeBS)	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10105
Goose and Swan Monitoring (GSMP)	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10106
Deep Sea Benthic Biodiversity (Multiple projects)	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/10239
Dogger Bank Mega-Epibenthos - Long term monitoring project	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/805
Eutrophication Monitoring & SmartBuoy in situ marine monitoring	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/940
Infrastructure de Recherche Littorale et Côtière (ILICO): SOMLIT (Roscoff)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/210
Infrastructure de Recherche Littorale et Côtière (ILICO): SOMLIT (Luc-sur-mer)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/232
Infrastructure de Recherche Littorale et Côtière (ILICO): SOMLIT (Gironde)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/348
Infrastructure de Recherche Littorale et Côtière (ILICO): SOMLIT (Arcachon)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/366
Infrastructure de Recherche Littorale et Côtière (ILICO): SOMLIT (Dinard)	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/519
Boknis Eck Underwater Observatory	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/801
ORCA Observations	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/955
ORCA Line Transect Distance Sampling	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/956
Nephrops Underwater Television Survey	https://edios.seadatanet.org/report/programme/11148
BALLT-D01234_FishOffshore	https://geonode.goosocean.org/api/layers/829